

Geographical Study Levels of Agricultural Performance in Vidarbha Region (2001-2006)

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Introduction:-

In the major challenge of the world in general underdeveloped and developing countries in particular area vast increase in population and corresponding upsurge in food demands. Food shortage is the severe problem in over populated country like India is mainly due to insufficient production of food grains despite best efforts in the form of green revolution has done. The causes for this are unfavorable weather condition, Socio-economic constraints and age old methods of farming which together prohibited the way of successful application of new farm technology which all accelerate farm production. Such constraints inevitable create imbalances in levels of food productivity. The level of agricultural performance as a concept means the degree to which the economic, cultural, technological and organization variables are able to exploit the abiotic resources of the area for agricultural production (Jasbir Singh 1997). The regional differences in yields per unit area indicate the impact of physical and non physical factors working in the area. Furthermore the level of agricultural performance is a dynamic concept and any sort of change in these factors affect agricultural productivity.

Objectives:-

Spatio characteristics of the level of agricultural performance provides a rational base for future orientation in agricultural planning. Keep this in view the major aims and objectives of the present paper is to delimit the area where agrarian development could not bring about significant changes in the crop structure and locate the weaker areas in terms of agricultural performance.

Hypothesis:-

Due to variations in physio co cultural set up level of performance of agriculture is diversified in the Nagpur division.

Methodology:-

Several techniques have been suggested by different scholar of agricultural Geography to work out the levels of agricultural productivity and performance. In this paper Jasbir Singh base of 1976 computing the Crop Yield and proportion of these crops in the total cropped area have been used. For objective measurement the relative yield and concentration indices arranged in ranking order and

computed into average ranking co-efficient. The formula is as fallows-

$$Y_i = \frac{Y_{ae}}{Y_{ar}} \times 100$$

Where,

Y_i – Crop Yield Index

Y_{ae} - the average yield per hectare of crop a in the cropped area in a unit

Y_{ar} – average yield of crop a in the entire region

$$C_i = \frac{P_{ae}}{P_{ar}} \times 100$$

Where,

Y_i – Crop concentration Index

Y_{ae} – percentage strength of crop a in cropped area of a unit

Y_{ar} – percentage strength of crop a in the entire region

Yield and concentration ranks for all crops are added and divided by 2. The equation according to Jasbir Singh crop yield and concentration-

$$\left[\begin{array}{c} \text{crop yield index} \\ \text{ranking of crop 'a'} \end{array} \right] + \left[\begin{array}{c} \text{crop concentration index} \\ \text{ranking of crop 'a'} \end{array} \right]$$

Indices ranking co - efficient for crop 'a' = $\frac{\left[\begin{array}{c} \text{crop yield index} \\ \text{ranking of crop 'a'} \end{array} \right] + \left[\begin{array}{c} \text{crop concentration index} \\ \text{ranking of crop 'a'} \end{array} \right]}{2} \times 100$

The result thus gives idea of level of agricultural performance the lower the ranking co-efficient, the higher the level of agricultural performance.

For the present study secondary data has been collected from Statistical Abstract 2005-06. In

the Vidarbha region number of crops cultivated; therefore only the table of Wheat crop is included for ready reference and results of all other crops included in the average ranking co-efficient table.

About the region:-

Vidarbha is a large political and socio region. This is the eastern part of Maharashtra State divided in two division Amravati and Nagpur. Till

1980-81 there were eight district. In the year 1992 Gadchiroli separated from Chandrapur and in may 1999 Gondia separated from Bhandara District. At present it comprise of 11 districts

The region is located between 17°51' N to 21°46' N and 75°57' E to 80°59' E. at the western border Buldhana and Gondia at the eastern corner. At the northern boundary of Vidarbha Satpuda range is extended. The total Geographical area of the region is 96536 Sq.Km.

The region is predominantly plateau in nature which is formed by ancient igneous rocks and basalt rocks. Average height from sea level is 300M. in Amravati, Buldhana and Akola west to east hills of Ajanta pre expended. In the region Wainganga, Purna, Painganga, Gadvi, Kanhan, Wardha, Tapi, Indravati, etc. are the main flowing rivers. In the region in summer temperature rages from 35 to 48°C. Chandrapur is the hottest while in winter it ranges from 11 to 30°C. the rainfall distribution in the region is very uneven. The rainfall increases from west to east. The black soil is available mainly in Nagpur, Amravati, Wardha, Yavatmal, Buldhana and Akola district; which is good for cotton cultivation. In the combination with this Gram, Rice, Wheat, Bajri, Jawar and Oilseeds are grown. In Bhandara and Gondia district Soil is rich in fermium elements; soil is suitable for rice cultivation here.

Irrigation is one of the major source for growing crops other than rainfall. For the development of agriculture canals, tanks, lakes and wells are important source of irrigation. In Vidarbha in the valley of Purna and Wardha oil seeds are grown in a large scale. In Buldhana and Yavatmal district cotton in combination with Rabi Jowar are grown. Other than in eastern Vidarbha Jowar,

wheat, oilseeds and other crops are grown o the basis of irrigation.

Crop yield and concentration of Rice in Vidarbha:-

Rice is the main crop of eastern Vidarbha particularly I Gondia, Chandrapur, Bhandara, Gadchiroli district. The highest yield of rice in the region is in chandrapur 1.88, then Wardha 1.67 and Nagpur 1.37, Gondia 0.83 and in Bhandara 0.73 while the regional average is 0.98 tonnes. Though area of the rice is maximum in Gondia district but on the basis of ratio with the regional average district is on the 6th rank and Wardha and Nagpur are on the first and second rank due to higher percentage of irrigated land. Of the total cropped area of Vidarbha region Rice share 11.4% and concentration of Rice is mainly in Gondia 76.3%, Gadchiroli 67.2% and Bhandara 56.9%. on the basis of crop yield and concentration indices. The result showed that Rice can be considered important from the point of agricultural performance in Wardha, Gondia, Chandrapur, Gadchiroli and Nagpur. While the crop in negligible in Wasim, Amravati, Akola and Buldhana district where ranking co-efficient is above 8. Thefore this area should be utilized for other crops.

Crop yield and concentration indices of Jowar:-

Yield of Jowar in the region is 0.20 tones per hector. Only Wardha district 0.18 and Gadchiroli 0.04 are below regional average. The maximum yield is in Amravati 1.12, Yavatmal 1.32 Buldhana 1.50 and Wasim 1.15 tones. On the basis of the yield indices in comparison to the region

whole Wasim ranks first, Buldhana second, Yavatmal third and Amravati fourth; while in the eastern Vidarbha yield ranks are on higher. On the basis of concentration indices of Jowar in the region is mainly in the western part of Vidarbha region.

Crop yield and concentration indices of Wheat:-

Wheat is not the important crop of the region where only 171800 hector area; where only 6% of the cropped area occupied by Wheat. The result of Wheat yield ranking shows that above the regional average Akola 146.39, Amravati 130.93, Wardha 119.59, Buldhana 110.31 and Nagpur 106%; while remaining districts are not important for the crop. The combined ranking co-efficient depict that from performance point of view Akola, Buldhana, Yavatmal and Nagpur, Wardha district are important district.

Table 1
Crop Yield and Concentration Indices of Wheat in Vidharbha 2005-06

S N	District	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	XIII	XIV	XV
		Pro. of Wheat	Area Under Wheat	Total Cropped Area	Yae I/II	Yar ΣI/ΣII	IV/V	VI x 100	Rank of Col VIII	Pae II/III	Par ΣII/ΣII I	Pae/Par IX/X	XI x 100	Rank of Col XII	VIII+ XIII	XIV/ 2
1	Buldhana	243	220	837	1.10	0.11	1.00	100	8	0.26	11.25	0.02	2	9.5	17.5	8.75
2	Akola	1980.2	9769	528	0.20	0.11	1.82	182	6	18.50	11.25	1.64	164	4	10	5
3	Washim	130	129	549	1.01	0.11	9.18	918	4	0.23	11.25	0.02	2	9.5	13.5	6.75
4	Amravati	172	140	1080	1.23	0.11	11.18	1118	1	0.18	11.25	0.02	2	9.5	10.5	5.25
5	Yavatmal	187	173	976	1.08	0.11	9.82	982	2	0.18	11.25	0.02	2	9.5	11.5	5.75
6	Wardha	1262	19396	387	0.06	0.11	0.54	54	10	50.12	11.25	4.45	445	1	11	5.5
7	Nagpur	336	326	597	1.03	0.11	9.36	936	3	0.55	11.25	0.05	5	7	10	5
8	Bhandara	916	10927	219	0.08	0.11	0.73	73	9	49.89	11.25	4.43	443	2	11	5.5
9	Gondia	674	3780	211	0.18	0.11	1.64	164	7	17.91	11.25	1.59	159	5	12	6
10	Chandrapur	749	22968	550	0.03	0.11	0.27	27	11	41.76	11.25	3.71	371	3	14	7
11	Gadchiroli	785	997	184	0.79	0.11	7.18	718	5	5.42	11.25	0.48	48	6	11	5.5
	Total	7434.2	68825	6118												

Crop yield and concentration indices of Pulses:-

The major Pulses growing in the region are Tur, Gram, Udad. Average yield of Pulses in the region is 0.57 tones. The districts Wardha 150.88, Yavatmal 121.05, Nagpur 110.53 and Wasim 101.75; while the yield is lowest in Gadchiroli 52.83. the combined yield and concentration indices shows that Yavatmal, Wardha, Wasim, Akola are the district where pulses are important crop in Agricultural performance point while in the eastern corner mainly in Gondia, Chandrapur and Gadchiroli the crop are not significant in the district economy.

Crop yield and concentration indices of Oilseeds:-

The average yield of Oilseeds in the region is 0.08 that indicated the relative insignificance of crop in the region. Though in some of the district yield is very high above the regional average i.e. highest in Buldhana 1.62 and in Gondia and Chandrapur 1.5. But the percentage share of the crop in these two districts are very meager. The combine performance of Oilseeds in the region is maximum in Buldhana and second Wasim then Chandrapur. Average crop

yield and concentration indices regional imbalance in overall agricultural performance.

On the basis of crop yield and concentration indices ranking co-efficient of the Rice, Wheat, Jowar, Cotton the total ranking co-efficient has been computed and for getting the average ranking co-efficient the result is divided by number of crops considered. The average ranking co-efficient for the Vidarbha is 5.99 and standard deviation is 0.70. the composite indices shows that spatio variations in the whole region are not very significant as it ranges from maximum 4.71 in Wardha to 6.96 in Gondia district. As it is stated at the beginning that lower the ranking co-efficient the higher the level of agricultural performance or productivity and vice versa.

In this context the whole Vidarbha is divided in three zones; they are-

Higher performance or Productivity level 4 to 5:-

Under this two districts are there i.e. Wardha and Akola. The region for higher productivity may be sighted due to rich black soil and means of well irrigation available here.

Table 2 Average Crop Yield and Concentration Indices in Vidharbha 2005-06

S N	District	Crop yield and concentration indices Ranking co-efficient of Rice	Crop yield and concentration indices Ranking co-efficient of Wheat	Crop yield and concentration indices Ranking co-efficient of Pulses	Crop yield and concentration indices Ranking co-efficient of Jowar	Crop yield and concentration indices Ranking co-efficient of Oilseeds	Crop yield and concentration indices Ranking co-efficient of Cotton	Total	Average Ranking of Co-efficient
1	Buldhana	7.75	8.75	6.5	4	5	4.5	36.5	6.08
2	Akola	9	5	3.5	4.5	4	3.5	29.5	4.92
3	Washim	10.5	6.75	3.5	4	5.5	3.5	33.75	5.62
4	Amravati	8	5.25	4.25	7	7.5	6.5	38.5	6.42
5	Yavatmal	8	5.75	3	5.5	10.5	5.5	38.25	6.37
6	Wardha	3	5.5	3.25	6.5	3.5	6.5	28.25	4.71
7	Nagpur	4	5	5.5	7.5	4.5	6.5	33	5.5
8	Bhandara	5.5	5.5	8	6.5	7.5	6.75	39.75	6.62
9	Gondia	3.5	6	9.5	8	6.5	8.25	41.75	6.96
10	Chandrapur	3.5	7	8.5	6.5	6.5	9	41	6.83
11	Gadchiroli	3.25	5.5	10.5	6	5	5	35.25	5.87

Moderate performance or Productivity level 5 to 6:-

This region comprises 4 districts Nagpur 5.5, Wasim 5.62, Gadchiroli 5.87 and Buldhana 6.08. in this region in Nagpur oilseeds, rice, wheat and pulses are important crops. In Gadchiroli this average ranking mainly comprising Rice followed by Jowar and oilseeds have shown better performance. In Buldhana too Jowar followed by Cotton and

oilseeds. This is the zone where cash crops or remunerative crops are playing vital role in agricultural economy.

Lower performance or Productivity level 6 to 7:-

The region is having lowest number of districts i.e. 5 out of 11; Yavatmal, Amravati, Bhandara, Gondia and Chnadrapur districts are under this category. The lowest average productivity is in Gondia district. The reason for this is due to

monoculture predominantly in maximum part and i.e. Rice. In Chandrapur due to increasing industrialization attention has not paid much to the development of the agriculture. In Yavatmal and Amravati due to overall performanve of various crops this co-efficient is higher.

Conclusion:-

In the Vidarbha region Agricultural performance or productivity is varying in nature though variations are not very high. On the basis of crop yield and concentration indices average ranking co-efficient three region have been demarcated high, moderate and low productivity region. Efforts has been made to co-relate ranking co-efficient score with rainfall amount and irrigated area district wise. The results of correlation between rainfall and productivity show moderate +0.53 correlation and with irrigation +0.66. it may be concluded that with the increase in irrigation and other Socio-economic factors level of productivity can be increased. So there is a need to focus on the development of few specific crops which are performing better in the district inspite of raising so many insignificant crops in the region. So that agricultural economy of the region may be strengthen.

References:-

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